

Title: A Scoping Review on Treatment Guidelines for Suspected Fungal Keratitis

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Introduction:

Fungal keratitis is a fungal infection of the cornea. Fungal keratitis can be difficult to diagnose, treat, and can lead to poor visual outcomes if not managed properly. Currently, there is a lack of literature on the decision making of when to start antifungal treatment based on the risk of suspected fungal keratitis. There can also be different pros and cons of starting treatment earlier for suspected cases of fungal keratitis. Currently, it is unclear how clinicians decide when or when not to start antifungal treatments.

A preliminary search was conducted and no current or underway systematic reviews or scoping reviews on the topic were identified.

The objective of this scoping review is to understand the extent of existing treatment guidelines and decision making for initiating treatment for suspected fungal keratitis.

Types of participants: Humans only (all geographical location, race, age, gender, and timeframe)

Inclusion Criteria:

- Studies which discuss global strategies/approaches on when to prescribe antifungal treatment
- Studies which discuss decision making related to using antifungal treatment,
- Studies which discuss practice patterns of fungal keratitis management
- Studies which discuss treatment guidelines for antifungal treatment
- Studies which discuss the benefits/risks of starting antifungal medications

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Non-English articles
2. Non-peer reviewed literature
3. Opinion, letter, or commentary articles
4. Any article does not discuss the management of fungal keratitis
5. Epidemiologic study
6. Reports on post-surgical fungal keratitis
7. Articles focusing on new diagnostic modalities
8. Articles with a narrowed focus (focusing on one organism, one treatment, or one specific location)
9. Articles focusing on efficacy of a specific treatment
10. Studies which include fewer than 3 patients or cases
11. Articles focusing on adjunct treatment of fungal keratitis
12. Articles that could not be retrieved in full text

Concept:

We are seeking to understand how clinicians make a decision when to start antifungal treatments for suspected fungal keratitis. We also plan to explore the pros and cons of starting antifungal treatment earlier for suspected fungal keratitis.

Context:

We aim to have a broad context of this scoping review. Any literature which meets the inclusion criteria will be included in the initial screening.

Types of evidence sources:

All available articles in scientific journals except opinion papers, editorials, and commentary

Methods:

We will follow the frameworks as previously published by Arksey and O'Malley¹ using the methods outlined in the JBI Manual for Evidence Synthesis.²

1. Arksey H, O'Malley L. Scoping studies: towards a methodological framework. *International Journal of Social Research Methodology*. 2005;8(1):19-32. doi:10.1080/1364557032000119616
2. Peters, M., Godfrey, C., McInerney, P. et al. In Z. Munn & E. Aromataris (Eds.), *JBI Manual for Evidence Synthesis*. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46658/JBIMES-20-01>

Search strategy:

A comprehensive and exhaustive search strategy will be developed by a health sciences informationist in the following databases: Ovid MEDLINE (R) ALL 1946 to DATE TBD, Embase.com, CINAHL Complete (EBSCO), Scopus.com, Web of Science (Core Collection), and Cochrane Library (Wiley) - limited to "Review protocols" and "Reviews". The search will be constructed around two primary concepts: "fungal keratitis" and "clinical decision making" using relevant controlled vocabulary, when available, for each included database and synonyms limited to appropriate keyword fields. We will not apply any language or date restrictions. The final draft of the Ovid MEDLINE search strategy is available at the end of this document.

Study/Source of evidence selection

Following the search, all identified citations will be collated and uploaded into Covidence and duplicates removed. Following a pilot test, titles and abstracts will then be screened by two or more independent reviewers for assessment against the inclusion criteria for the

review. Potentially relevant sources will be retrieved in full and their citation details imported into a secure database that can be accessed by team members only. The full text of selected citations will be assessed in detail against the inclusion criteria by two or more independent reviewers. Reasons for exclusion of sources of evidence at full text that do not meet the inclusion criteria will be recorded and reported in the scoping review. Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers at each stage of the selection process will be resolved with an additional reviewer. The results of the search and the study inclusion process will be reported in full in the final scoping review and presented in a PRISMA flow diagram as presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Scoping review process

Data extraction:

Data will be extracted from papers included in the scoping review by two or more independent reviewers using a data extraction tool developed by the reviewers. The data extracted will include specific details about the participants, concept, context, study methods and key findings relevant to the review questions.

The draft data extraction tool will be modified and revised as necessary during the process of extracting data from each included evidence source. Modifications will be detailed in the scoping review. Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers will be resolved with an additional reviewer. If appropriate, authors of papers will be contacted to request missing or additional data, where required.

Specifically, the scoping review data extraction will include the following data from each data source if available.

1. Article title
2. List of authors
3. Year of publication
4. Location of population included in the study
5. Primary aim of the study
6. Secondary aim of the study
7. Study type
8. Type(s) of organism
9. Relevant conclusions
10. Specific clinical risk factors that suggest fungal keratitis
11. Other considerations when clinicians decide to start antifungal medications
12. Defined protocol/guideline for prescribing antifungal medications mentioned in the data source
13. Specific benefits of starting antifungal medications
14. Specific risks of stating antifungal medications
15. Antifungal medications discussed
16. Preferred antifungal medication(s) for fungal keratitis

Data analysis and presentation:

Frequency counts will be used to assess the presence and absence of each type of data extracted. The results will be present in tables or graphs.

Search Terms:

Ovid MEDLINE <https://www.lib.umich.edu/database/link/8859>

[Ovid MEDLINE\(R\) ALL 1946 to August 07, 2025](#)

1.

(Keratitis/ OR Keratoconjunctivitis/ OR Corneal Ulcer/ OR (Keratitis OR Keratitides OR ((corneae OR corneal OR cornea OR corneas) adj3 (ulcer OR ulcus OR ulcers OR ulceration OR ulcerative))).tw.) AND (exp "Eye Infections, Fungal"/ OR exp Fungi/ OR (Fungal OR Fungi OR Non-viral OR Non-bacterial OR atypical).tw.) OR ("Fungal ulcer*" OR Keratomycosis).tw.

4612

2.

exp "Antifungal Agents"/ OR exp "Clinical Decision Rules"/ OR exp "Clinical Decision-Making"/ OR exp "Decision Making"/ OR exp "Decision Making, Shared"/ OR exp "Decision Support Techniques"/ OR exp "Decision Trees"/ OR exp "Drug Synergism"/ OR exp "Drug Therapy, Combination"/ OR exp "Guidelines as Topic"/ OR exp Natamycin/ OR exp "Practice Patterns, Physicians"/ OR exp Voriconazole/ OR dt.xs. OR tu.xs. OR ("practice pattern*" OR antifungal OR decision* OR delay* OR drug* OR guideline* OR initiation OR management OR medication* OR prescrib* OR protocol* OR treatment* OR voriconazole OR natamycin).ti,kw. OR ("practice pattern*" OR decision* OR guideline* OR prescrib* OR protocol*).ab.

9281041

1 AND 2: 2596 results on 9/2/25

(34096156 OR 30590103 OR 36256441 OR 30562337 OR 21670358 OR 39312711).ui.

Embase <http://www.lib.umich.edu/database/link/9173>

1.

('keratitis'/de OR 'microbial keratitis'/exp OR 'filamentary keratitis'/exp OR 'suppurative keratitis'/exp OR 'contact lens keratitis'/de OR 'cornea ulcer'/de OR ('keratitis' OR 'keratitides' OR ((corneae OR corneal OR cornea OR corneas) NEAR/3 (ulcer OR ulcus OR ulcers OR ulceration OR ulcerative))):ti,ab,kw AND ('fungal eye infection'/exp OR 'fungus'/exp OR ('fungal' OR 'fungi' OR 'non-viral' OR 'non-bacterial' OR 'atypical'):ti,ab,kw) OR ('keratomycosis'/exp OR ('fungal ulcer*' OR 'keratomycosis'):ti,ab,kw)

7005

2.

'clinical decision rule'/exp OR 'clinical decision making'/exp OR 'decision making'/exp OR 'shared decision making'/exp OR 'decision support system'/exp OR 'decision tree'/exp OR 'practice guideline'/exp OR 'clinical practice'/exp OR ("practice pattern*" OR antifungal OR decision* OR delay* OR drug* OR guideline* OR initiation OR management OR medication* OR prescrib* OR protocol* OR treatment* OR voriconazole OR natamycin):ti,kw OR ("practice pattern*" OR decision* OR guideline* OR prescrib* OR protocol*):ab

7,459,846

1 AND 2: 2005 results on 9/2/25

(34096156 OR 30590103 OR 36256441 OR 30562337 OR 21670358 OR 39312711):ui

CINAHL Complete (EBSCO) <http://www.lib.umich.edu/database/link/9911>

1.

((MH "Keratitis" OR MH "Corneal Ulcer" OR XB(Keratitis OR Keratitides OR ((corneae OR corneal OR cornea OR corneas) N3 (ulcer OR ulcus OR ulcers OR ulceration OR ulcerative)))) AND (MH "Eye Infections, Fungal" OR XB(Fungal OR Fungi OR Non-viral OR Non-bacterial OR atypical))) OR MH "Keratitis, Fungal" OR XB("Fungal ulcer*" OR Keratomycosis)

481 results

2.

MH "Antifungal Agents+" OR MH "Decision Making" OR MH "Decision Making, Clinical+" OR MH "Decision Making, Shared" OR MH "Drug Therapy" OR MH "Guideline Adherence" OR MH "Practice Guidelines" OR MH "Practice Patterns" OR MH "Prescribing Patterns" OR XB("practice pattern*" OR antifungal OR decision* OR delay* OR drug* OR guideline* OR initiation OR management OR medication* OR natamycin OR prescrib* OR protocol* OR treatment* OR voriconazole)

2258742

1 AND 2: [328 results](#) on 9/2/25

Scopus <http://www.lib.umich.edu/database/link/10049>

(TITLE (((((keratitis OR keratitides OR ((cornea OR corneae OR corneal OR corneas) W/2 (ulcer OR ulceration OR ulcerative OR ulcers OR ulcus))) AND (atypical OR fungal OR fungi OR non-bacterial OR non-viral)) OR "fungal ulcer*" OR keratomycosis) AND (management OR "practice pattern*" OR decision* OR guideline* OR prescrib* OR protocol* OR delay* OR initiation OR treatment*))) OR KEY (((((keratitis OR keratitides OR ((cornea OR corneae OR corneal OR corneas) W/2 (ulcer OR ulceration OR ulcerative OR ulcers OR ulcus))) AND (atypical OR fungal OR fungi OR non-bacterial OR non-viral)) OR "fungal ulcer*" OR keratomycosis) AND (management OR "practice pattern*" OR decision* OR guideline* OR prescrib* OR protocol* OR delay* OR initiation OR treatment*)))) OR

(ABS (((((keratitis OR keratitides OR ((cornea OR corneae OR corneal OR corneas) W/2 (ulcer OR ulceration OR ulcerative OR ulcers OR ulcus))) AND (atypical OR fungal OR fungi OR non-bacterial OR non-viral)) OR "fungal ulcer*" OR keratomycosis) AND ("practice pattern*" OR decision* OR guideline* OR prescrib* OR protocol*))))

[1713 results](#) on 9/2/25

Web of Science <http://www.lib.umich.edu/database/link/10165>

Core Collection

Exact search enabled

TI=(((keratitis OR keratitides OR ((cornea OR corneae OR corneal OR corneas) NEAR/2 (ulcer OR ulceration OR ulcerative OR ulcers OR ulcer))) AND (atypical OR fungal OR fungi OR non-bacterial OR non-viral)) OR "fungal ulcer*" OR keratomycosis) AND ("practice pattern*" OR antifungal OR decision* OR drug* OR guideline* OR management OR medication* OR natamycin OR prescrib* OR protocol* OR voriconazole)) OR
KP=(((keratitis OR keratitides OR ((cornea OR corneae OR corneal OR corneas) NEAR/2 (ulcer OR ulceration OR ulcerative OR ulcers OR ulcer))) AND (atypical OR fungal OR fungi OR non-bacterial OR non-viral)) OR "fungal ulcer*" OR keratomycosis) AND ("practice pattern*" OR antifungal OR decision* OR drug* OR guideline* OR management OR medication* OR natamycin OR prescrib* OR protocol* OR voriconazole)) OR
AK=(((keratitis OR keratitides OR ((cornea OR corneae OR corneal OR corneas) NEAR/2 (ulcer OR ulceration OR ulcerative OR ulcers OR ulcer))) AND (atypical OR fungal OR fungi OR non-bacterial OR non-viral)) OR "fungal ulcer*" OR keratomycosis) AND ("practice pattern*" OR antifungal OR decision* OR drug* OR guideline* OR management OR medication* OR natamycin OR prescrib* OR protocol* OR voriconazole))

[778 results](#) on 8/21/25